

Channel Prediction in 6G Non-Terrestrial Networks With Deep Learning: a Physical Layer Analysis

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Abstract—Channel prediction on the user equipment side has recently been identified as one of the main use cases for artificial intelligence in the radio access network. With advanced neural networks, complex channel dynamics can be predicted from current channel estimates, allowing for demodulation reference signals to be transmitted at a lower rate. Reducing reliance on pilot symbols for channel estimation frees valuable resources for data transmission, but this requires highly accurate predictions of future channel states. This paper introduces a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN)-based encoder-decoder model designed to predict the time-frequency channel response matrix in orthogonal frequency division multiplexing systems. The proposed approach alternates pilot-full and pilot-free slots, leveraging deep learning to predict channel conditions over the latter while maintaining link quality. Through extensive simulations, we assess the model’s effectiveness on key physical layer metrics, with a particular focus on the effective throughput (TP). We show that the proposed predictor achieves TP gains of up to 8% with respect to channel estimation for high modulation orders; on the other hand, low modulation orders’ performance at low energy per bit over noise power spectral density suffer from inaccurate channel predictions. The predictor’s lightweight design, requiring only 160k multiply and accumulate operations and encompassing 5.5k parameters, ensures feasibility for real-time applications in next-generation networks.

Index Terms—Non-Terrestrial Networks, Channel Prediction, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Satellite communications (SatCom) has seen a surge in popularity in the recent decade, with non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) being recognized as one of the key technologies to achieve ubiquitous connectivity in the 6th generation (6G) of cellular communication standards [1]. Indeed, constellations of satellites, possibly at different altitudes, can be used to provide global coverage on Earth from space. When non-geostationary satellite orbit (NGSO) satellites are considered, NTNs bring several channel impairments into play due to the inherent dynamicity of the system, *e.g.*, time-varying Doppler frequency shift, delay, and attenuations; moreover, frequency selective fading due to multipath should also be taken into account, albeit with typically fewer channel taps than in terrestrial networks [2]. In an effort to counteract such effects, communication systems reserve resources for the transmission of predefined pilot sequences, which the receiver can exploit to synchronize and estimate the channel conditions. Clearly, this approach leaves a lower amount of resources available for data transmission, reducing the overall throughput; thus, the number of pilot resources should be kept

at a minimum. For this reason, over the course of the years many studies have focused on the possibility to predict the future channel conditions. With the advance of deep learning (DL), neural networks (NNs) have been proposed as possible predictors in NTNs, with a particular emphasis on recurrent NNs (RNNs), such as long short-term memory (LSTM), and convolutional NNs (CNNs). Furthermore, channel prediction on the user equipment (UE) side is one of the use cases identified in the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) group for the application of artificial intelligence in the radio access network [3]. In [4], an LSTM was trained to predict a sequence of multiple input multiple output (MIMO) channel matrices from a time series of estimated MIMO channel matrices. The authors evaluated the normalized mean squared error (NMSE) on the predicted channel matrices, observing a decrease in NMSE by 7 dB and 10 dB with respect to an RNN and a Kalman filter predictor, respectively. An LSTM was also implemented in [5] for time division duplexing SatCom systems, with the model predicting future downlink channel coefficients from uplink channel estimates relayed by UEs. The authors compared the NMSE achieved by the proposed predictor and that of aged channel coefficients with respect to the actual downlink channel coefficients. This approach is especially beneficial to digital beamforming in NGSO-based NTNs, as the technique relies on the feedback of downlink channel estimates from UEs: due to time-varying nature of the channel, such channel estimates may be misaligned with respect to the actual channel conditions encountered at transmission time (the so-called channel aging effect), worsening the beamforming performance [6]. The predictor proposed in [7] aimed at obtaining the future downlink channel matrix from a channel matrix estimated in the uplink, exploiting channel correlations in frequency division duplexing systems. The prediction is achieved through convolutional and LSTM layers to better extract both spatial and temporal correlations. A similar model was also employed in [8] for channel coefficients time series prediction in a DL-based multi-beam precoding scheme. Thorough system-level analyses showed that the model produces more accurate predictions with respect to simple LSTMs and RNNs, resulting in an improved weighted sum-rate. Finally, the authors in [9] exploited the geometrical relationship between user location and channel coefficients to predict a user’s channel coefficients without channel knowledge using a deep NN. The predictions were employed to perform cell-free MIMO downlink transmissions

from a LEO satellite, increasing the achieved capacity 10%-ile by up to 15% with respect to outdated channel coefficients and halving the outage probability.

The literature shows that channel prediction is a promising technique for NTN that can serve both to counteract channel aging in MIMO systems and to reduce the number of pilots transmitted. However, its implications at the link level should be assessed to ensure that the predicted channel matrices can be effectively employed to equalize received transmissions. Indeed, as the prediction inaccuracy is often reported in terms of mean squared error (MSE) with respect to the actual channel matrix, the distribution over time and frequency of the prediction error is often neglected; nevertheless, it is reasonable to assume that the prediction uncertainty increases with time. Such effects require dedicated analyses to assess their impact on physical layer metrics, *e.g.*, bit error rate (BER) and block error rate (BLER). Furthermore, the effective throughput (TP) should also be evaluated to ensure that the gain resulting from the increased number of resources available for data transmission overcomes the loss due to channel uncertainty in channel prediction. Thus, motivated by these considerations, in this paper we:

- Propose an OFDM resource grid structure in which pilot-full slots are alternated with pilot-free slots to reduce the pilot frequency;
- Train a lightweight encoder-decoder CNN-based channel predictor that performs a time-series-based prediction of the future time-frequency channel response matrix;
- Evaluate the performance of the predictor with respect to channel estimation under a tapped delay line (TDL) channel model in a link-level simulation in terms of BER, BLER, and TP under different modulation orders, highlighting the TP gains achieved through channel prediction.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a single low earth orbit (LEO) satellite in a NTN providing downlink connectivity to a set of UEs. We here focus on ground UEs with limited mobility, but the analysis can be extended to other terminals, *e.g.*, on board of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) or drones. The transmission and reception chains are based on the 5G specifics using orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) with frequency synchronization error within 5G requirements, *i.e.*, 0.1 parts per million (ppm) of the carrier frequency [10]. On the transmitter side, the data bits at the physical layer are processed with low density parity check (LDPC) channel encoding, bit interleaving, M -ary quadrature amplitude modulation (M-QAM) mapping, pilot symbols insertion, and multiplexing to generate the OFDM resource grid \mathbf{X} of size (N_{SC}, N_{sym}) . We here focus on a temporal window of 2 slots, *i.e.*, $N_{sym} = 2N_{sym}^{(slot)}$, where $N_{sym}^{(slot)} = 14$ represents the number of OFDM symbols per time slot. We consider a tapped delay line (TDL) channel with a residual frequency synchronization error, under the assumption that the Doppler shift due to the satellite movement is compensated up to a

Fig. 1. Channel prediction framework (blue and orange squares correspond to data and pilot symbols, respectively).

residual error component. Thus, the channel impulse response can be written as:

$$h(t, \tau) = e^{j2\pi\epsilon_D t} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{taps}} h_n(t) \delta(\tau - \tau_n), \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_D \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_D)$ represents the residual frequency synchronization error, N_{taps} is the number of paths in the considered model, $h_n(t)$ represents the n -th tap's complex coefficient, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac's delta function, and τ_n is the n -th tap's delay (typically normalized with respect to the first tap's delay, *i.e.*, $\tau_1 = 0$). At the receiver, the M-QAM symbols carried by the waveform are de-multiplexed and equalized with known channel coefficients, typically assessed through channel estimation on pilots. De-mapping extracts the bit log-likelihood ratios (LLRs) associated to each equalized symbol, and bit de-interleaving and channel decoding are carried out to obtain the recovered data sequence. We assume that quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK)-modulated pilots are present on each subcarrier (*i.e.*, block-type pilot arrangement) at OFDM symbol indices \mathcal{I}_π , repeating on each slot the pilot allocation at indices $\mathcal{I}_\pi^{(slot)} \subseteq [1, N_{sym}^{(slot)}]$. The resource grid after OFDM de-multiplexing can be expressed with the following typical matricial formulation:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H} \odot \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{W}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H} = FFT[h(t, \tau)]$ is the $N_{SC} \times N_{sym}$ channel frequency response (CFR) matrix, \mathbf{W} represents additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance $N_0/2$ (with N_0 being the noise power spectral density), and \odot is the Hadamard (*i.e.*, element-wise) multiplication operator. With channel estimation, symbols are collected from the received OFDM grid at the pilots location $\mathbf{Y}_\pi = \mathbf{Y}[:, \mathcal{I}_\pi]$ and processed with the known value of the transmitted pilots $\mathbf{X}_\pi = \mathbf{X}[:, \mathcal{I}_\pi]$ to estimate the channel coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_\pi$ at such locations in the grid, *e.g.*, through least square (LS); interpolation is then used to obtain the estimated CFR matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ over the

Fig. 2. Diagram of the proposed CNN.

entire grid [11]. Clearly, the effectiveness of interpolation is affected by the frequency of pilot transmission with respect to the channel dynamics; hence, each OFDM slot typically contains at least one pilot OFDM symbol to estimate the channel on a slot basis. However, the literature has shown that DL methods can predict future channel conditions on the short term based on time series of current or previous channel samples. Thus, in our channel prediction framework we alternate a typical OFDM slot with a pilot-free slot that only contains data symbols (Figure 1). In the first slot, channel estimation can be carried out with traditional estimation techniques thanks to the presence of pilot symbols; then, the resulting channel estimates $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{est} = \hat{\mathbf{H}}[:, 1 : N_{sym}^{(slot)}]$ are fed to the channel predictor to assess the future CFR matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{pred} \approx \mathbf{H}[:, N_{sym}^{(slot)} + 1 : 2 \cdot N_{sym}^{(slot)}]$, which can finally be used to equalize and demodulate the pilot-free slot.

III. CNN-BASED CHANNEL PREDICTOR

The architecture of the channel prediction NN is a lightweight encoder-decoder structure based on convolutional layers (Figure 2). In the encoding section of the NN, the input tensor $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{in}$ is fed to a series of 2D convolutional (Conv2D) layers with no padding, batch normalization (BN) layers, and leaky rectified linear unit (LReLU) activation functions. The objective of Conv2D layers is to learn to extract temporal and spatial features from the input channel matrix in a similar fashion to image processing. The i -th Conv2D layer applies $N^{(i)}$ learnt filters of size $W_f^{(i)} \times W_t^{(i)}$ (where subscripts f and t refer to the time and frequency axes, respectively), sliding over their $L_f^{(i)} \times L_t^{(i)} \times C^{(i)}$ input tensor. The stride parameter (S_f, S_t) can also be set to increase the sliding step, *i.e.*, each filter is applied every S_f and S_t elements of the input tensor, respectively, further reducing the size of the $L_f^{(i+1)} \times L_t^{(i+1)} \times N^{(i)}$ output tensor (note that $C^{(i+1)} = N^{(i)}$). BN improves the training process by normalizing the output of each Conv2D layer, while LReLU introduces non-linearities in the features extracted by Conv2D. At the output of the encoding section is a compact tensor containing the relevant compressed information of the input tensor. Thus, the decoding section mirrors the previous operation, aiming

at constructing the predicted CFR over the following slot. To achieve this, Conv2D layers are substituted with Transpose Conv2D (TConv2D) layers, which upsample their input tensor by performing the transpose of the convolution operation. The implementation of the encoding-decoding structure strongly reduces the computational complexity of the channel predictor; more details on this will be discussed in Section V. Finally, we note that, for this particular architecture, the addition of skip connections did not provide meaningful loss improvements.

A. CNN input

As a pre-processing step, the estimated channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{est}$, obtained through LS and interpolation, is normalized to unit average power and split into the two components of its polar representation. The base 10 logarithm of its amplitude and its pi-scaled phase are then stacked together in an additional dimension to form the real-valued input tensor $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{in}$ of size $(N_{SC}, N_{sym}^{(slot)}, 2)$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{in} = \left[10 \log_{10} \left| \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{est} \right| ; (\angle \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{est}) / \pi \right], \quad (3)$$

where $\angle x$ returns the argument of the complex value x in the range $[-\pi, \pi]$. We note that the Cartesian representation of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{est}$ has also been tested as NN input, but ultimately discarded due to higher loss during training.

B. CNN output

The output of the CNN reflects the features of the input tensor, *i.e.*, $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{out}$ is a tensor of size $(N_{SC}, N_{sym}^{(slot)}, 2)$, with the two channels containing magnitude and phase scaled information. Thus, the predicted complex channel can be obtained as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{pred} = 10^{0.1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{out}[:, :, 1]} \cdot e^{j\pi \hat{\mathbf{H}}_{out}[:, :, 2]}. \quad (4)$$

C. Loss function

As channel prediction is regarded as a regression task, the MSE was the considered loss function to be minimized during training. We note that, due to power normalization, this coincides with NMSE (CFRs have been normalized to unit average power).

D. Dataset, training, and inference

The encoding and decoding sections of the CNN are jointly pre-trained on a synthetic dataset that is generated on demand, *i.e.*, during each training epoch a batch of N_{batch} pairs of estimated CFRs and channel matrices to be predicted are generated according to the system model described in Section II. We improve the training process through several techniques, among which are early stopping, L2 regularization, and learning rate decay on loss plateaus. In this work, the CNN is trained offline and deployed for inference. Nonetheless, we note that online learning frameworks, *e.g.*, continuous learning, could also be investigated to ensure adequate prediction accuracy regardless of the channel model. More in general, a comparison between generalization and adaptability of channel predictors should be thoroughly carried out, taking into account a broad range of aspects, *e.g.*, computational complexity.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Training E_b/N_0 range	$E_b/N_0 = [0, 1, \dots, 10]$ [dB]
Maximum Monte Carlo Iterations	$N_{MC} = 10^5$
Data modulation order	$M = \{4, 16, 64\}$
Pilot modulation order	$M_\pi = 4$
Code rate	$R_c = 3/4$
Training channel model	NTN-TDL-C [2]
UE speed	3 km/h
Carrier frequency	$f_c = 2$ GHz
Number of subcarriers	$N_{SC} = 48$
Number of OFDM symbols	$N_{sym} = 28$
5G numerology	$\mu = 0$
Pilot indices per slot	$\mathcal{I}_\pi^{(slot)} = [3, 12]$
Batch size	$N_B = 4096$
Initial learning rate	0.01
Learning rate decay factor	10
Learning rate decay patience	50 epochs
Early stopping patience	150 epochs
L2 regularization factor	10^{-6}

IV. RESULTS

We here discuss the simulation results of the proposed channel predictor for NTN. Table I reports the main simulation parameters. The CNN is trained and evaluated in the MATLAB computing environment, making use of toolboxes such as the 5G Toolbox and the Deep Learning Toolbox. The training channel model is NTN-TDL-C, while the residual frequency synchronization error is Gaussian-distributed with standard deviation $\sigma_D = \frac{0.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot f_c}{3}$, *i.e.*, the frequency error does not exceed 0.1 ppm of the carrier frequency 99.7% of the times (the so-called 3σ rule). Figure 3 shows a mesh plot of the MSE achieved by the proposed model as a function of the energy per bit over noise power spectral density ratio (E_b/N_0) and the OFDM symbol index. One can identify two approximately linear trends for the MSE over the symbol index: until the fourth OFDM symbol, the prediction MSE increases by 0.01 every symbol; on the other hand, for the subsequent OFDM symbols the MSE goes up by 0.015 every symbol index. Clearly, this reflects the uncertainty in channel prediction as the prediction window goes further in the future. While this trend is evident at low E_b/N_0 , it is not pronounced after $E_b/N_0 = 6$ dB. Indeed, after this threshold the channel prediction accuracy on QPSK symbols is not noise-limited anymore, and the MSE does not exceed 0.01 in the considered E_b/N_0 range.

A. Bit Error Rate

Focusing on the end-to-end simulation, we first assess the uncoded BER as a function of the E_b/N_0 . Here, a hard decision is taken on the bit LLRs at the output of the demodulator, and their value is compared with that at the transmitter after LDPC encoding. We compare the BER achieved by the channel predictor with an estimation-only scheme, in which pilots are transmitted in both time slots and no prediction is performed, and the theoretical bit error

Fig. 3. MSE as a function of E_b/N_0 and the OFDM symbol index.

Fig. 4. BER as a function of E_b/N_0 .

probability curve in a pure AWGN channel. For each data modulation order, an estimation-limited BER region can be identified: here, the estimation accuracy is too low for the CNN to provide good channel predictions, thus resulting in a slower BER decay, *e.g.*, until 4 dB of E_b/N_0 for QPSK. Clearly, as pilot symbols are also QPSK, this threshold roughly coincides with that for MSE improvement as seen in Figure 3. We also note that channel estimation sees a larger gap in performance with respect to the theoretical AWGN BER curve until such E_b/N_0 value. Nonetheless, for high E_b/N_0 the prediction-aided system achieves satisfying performance, *e.g.*, with a gap smaller than 0.5 dB and 1.5 dB for QPSK and 16-QAM, respectively, at $BER = 10^{-3}$. As the modulation order increases, the performance gap becomes more evident, and the channel prediction curve with 64-QAM tends to diverge early from the channel estimation performance.

B. Block Error Rate

As expected, the BER plots highlighted that several errors are introduced in the received bits due to channel prediction; thus, in order to assess the benefits over channel estimation,

Fig. 5. BLER as a function of E_b/N_0 (code rate $R_c = 3/4$).

the BLER must be evaluated. Figure 5 shows that the QPSK-modulated transport blocks are often erroneously received, with the classic waterfall trend only starting after the MSE improvement at $E_b/N_0 = 4$ dB. Clearly, this gap suggests that channel prediction is not a viable solution for QPSK-modulated symbols, as the channel estimation BLER curve for 16-QAM surpasses that for channel prediction with QPSK after 5 dB of E_b/N_0 ; however, this statement should be further assessed through different coding rates and DL models with similar complexity. On the opposite, the gap between channel estimation and channel prediction for 16-QAM data symbols is smaller than 1 dB at around 1% of BLER, but the waterfall trend is broken by an error floor well below 10^{-3} . Such behavior is more clear for the 64-QAM plot, as the small channel prediction MSE still induces too many errors in demodulation, resulting in an error floor around 1% of BLER. This is to be expected, as NNs act as function approximators: indeed, the more accurate the approximation is, the lower the error floor would be. However, this typically is achieved through the use of either deeper or wider CNNs to extract more complex features, increasing the overall computational complexity of the model.

C. Throughput

Up until this point, the benefits of channel predictions have not been highlighted yet. Indeed, a higher error rate in both received bits and blocks has been observed, but it is yet to be assessed whether the amount of additional data symbols resulting from the removal of pilots on the second slot outweighs the BLER gap. We evaluate this by computing the effective TP achieved by the system:

$$TP_e = \frac{m \cdot R_c \cdot N_{SC} \cdot (N_{sym}^{(slot)} - |\mathcal{I}_{\pi}^{(slot)}|)}{T_{slot}} \cdot (1 - BLER_e), \quad (5)$$

$$TP_p = \frac{TP_e + \frac{m \cdot R_c \cdot N_{SC} \cdot N_{sym}^{(slot)}}{T_{slot}} (1 - BLER_p)}{2}, \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6. Throughput as a function of E_b/N_0 (code rate $R_c = 3/4$).

where subscripts e and p refer to estimation and prediction, respectively, $m = \log_2 M$ representing the number of bits per data symbol, and $T_{slot} = 1ms$ being the OFDM slot duration for the chosen 5G numerology. Figure 6 shows that the proposed model is not able to provide significant TP gains for QPSK data transmissions. Indeed, although the peak throughput with channel prediction is higher than with channel estimation, the TP can be doubled at the same E_b/N_0 level by moving to 16-QAM. On the other hand, the gains of channel prediction at higher modulation orders are evident. For 16-QAM, the prediction curve overtakes channel estimation after $E_b/N_0 = 5.5$ dB and reaches a TP of 1.87 Mbps at 7 dB, an 8% gain over channel estimation. Similarly, the two 64-QAM curves cross at 9.75 dB, with channel prediction reaching 2.77 Mbps at 12 dB of E_b/N_0 against the 2.59 Mbps achieved by channel estimation. Clearly, the TP at the highest modulation order is also limited by the high BLER error floor, as discussed in Section IV-B; to achieve a steeper TP increase and reach the peak TP at an earlier E_b/N_0 , a more accurate DL model should be used, possibly requiring additional complexity.

V. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY

With the CNN being considered for implementation in UEs, it is imperative to assess the number of operations required to run the model and ensure that the prediction can be carried out within the communication system's requirements. We focus on the number of multiply and accumulate (MAC) units, which we here upper bound by the number of multiplications in Conv2D and TConv2D layers (the remaining layers' complexity is negligible). The number of multiplications at layer i can be evaluated as:

$$Mul_i^{(Conv2D)} = L_f^{(i+1)} L_t^{(i+1)} N^{(i)} W_f^{(i)} W_t^{(i)} C^{(i)}, \quad (7)$$

$$Mul_i^{(TConv2D)} = L_f^{(i)} L_t^{(i)} N^{(i)} W_f^{(i)} W_t^{(i)} C^{(i)}, \quad (8)$$

where the output tensor, generated using $N^{(i)}$ filters with size $W_f^{(i)} \times W_t^{(i)}$, has $C^{(i+1)} = N^{(i)}$ channels with shape

$(L_f^{(i+1)}, L_t^{(i+1)})$). Recalling the CNN scheme (Figure 2), this results in approximately 160k MACs for the prediction of the CFR matrix over one time slot and $N_{SC} = 48$ subcarriers, or 40k MACs per physical resource block. Clearly, the actual temporal duration for the prediction of a channel matrix depends on the available hardware and specific implementations. However, the advances of specialized hardware accelerators can make real-time DL at the physical layer a reality. Indeed, the authors in [12] implemented a CNN on board of a nano-UAV for a real-time image processing task, achieving 139 inferences/s or, equivalently, 7.19 ms/inference, with low power requirements. Scaling down such value based on our model's complexity (160k MACs) with respect to the author's (1.1M MACs), our model can be run with such hardware at approximately 1 ms/inference. As the inference time coincides with the slot duration, we conclude that our channel prediction model can run in real time: indeed, assuming negligible time is required to estimate the channel over the first slot, the prediction will be ready as soon as the following slot is received. Furthermore, we note that a faster or less power-hungry predictor may be achieved with the implementation of different DL architectures or NN compression techniques [13]. We also note that the proposed model only requires 5.5k parameters, leading to a compact memory footprint.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented a lightweight DL-based channel prediction module for OFDM-based downlink transmissions in NTN. The predictor is based on an encoding-decoding CNN that extracts channel statistics from an estimated CFR and projects them to the future to predict the upcoming channel matrix, reducing the overall amount of transmitted pilot symbols. Extensive Monte Carlo simulations evaluated the effective TP gain with respect to pilot transmission and channel estimation on every slot. The results revealed that low order modulations, *e.g.*, QPSK, may not benefit from channel prediction at low E_b/N_0 due to large inaccuracies in the predicted CFRs. On the other hand, higher order modulations benefit from the reduced pilot signals, with 16-QAM transmissions achieving a TP gain of about 8% at $E_b/N_0 = 7.5$ dB. The trainable parameters of the model are only 5.5k and the required MACs are 160k, making the proposed CNN able to be run in real time. Nonetheless, many research questions are still open for channel prediction in NTNs. Firstly, channel prediction models should be evaluated with real data; however, such information for NTN is hard to obtain. Secondly, the generalization capabilities of DL models with respect to different channel models should be assessed. Although we did not extensively test the training-test channel model mismatch, we note that we empirically observed similar TP on the second 3GPP LoS channel model, NTN-TDL-D, but far worse TP on the non-LoS channel models NTN-TDL-A and -B. Thus, on the one hand, generalization-focused training schemes could be considered for future works. On the other hand, online training paradigms could also be exploited to adaptively fit DL models to the current channel conditions.

Finally, we note that data-aided channel estimation schemes could be applied on prediction-equalized symbols to increase the number of consecutive pilot-free slots.

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